

A Journey in the Land of Contradictions: The depiction of Romania in Swedish guidebooks 1964–1981

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Abstract

In the construction of countries as tourist destinations, travel literature – such as guidebooks – plays an integral role in deciding what places to visit and how these should be perceived. The Socialist Republic of Romania began a large-scale investment in its tourism industry in the 1950s, with ambitions of improving both its economic situation and international image. This initiative initially proved successful, as the country saw an increase in tourism from Western Europe, not least from Scandinavian countries. This paper focuses on how Swedish guidebooks published between 1964 and 1981 depicted Romania as a desirable tourist destination. These guidebooks were analysed qualitatively through the use of thematization and comparative analysis, taking into account their context of production. Using the theoretical frameworks of the tourist gaze and Balkanism, this study shows that the guidebooks construct a gaze of Romania as a semi-place – where Western influences meet Eastern, and the ancient meets the modern. The perspective of the tourist is of great importance in the construction of the gaze, as it determines which aspects of the country, modern versus ancient, are perceived as positive or negative. The perceived authenticity of the countryside, where time has seemingly stood still and where traditions are upheld, is a prominent and integral part of this gaze in the analysed guidebooks. Furthermore, similarities can be observed between the depiction within the guidebooks and the official image pushed by the Romanian tourism industry, both in the focus on the authentic

countryside, as well as in the emphasis on the authentic countryside and the nation's historical narrative centered on its Roman legacy. As this was a formative period for the Romanian tourism industry, it was equally guiding in the shaping of the Western tourist gaze of the country. By analyzing these guidebooks, this study contributes to the existing scholarship on Western perceptions of Eastern Europe, offering new insights into how Romania was depicted as a tourist destination during the Cold War era.

Keywords: Romania, tourist gaze, guidebooks, Sweden/Swedish

Introduction

“Not so many years ago, Romania was one of Europe's most neglected countries from a tourism perspective. It seemed remote and isolated. Now, Romania has opened its gates wide to tourists and will surely rank among the top tourist destinations of the 1970s.”⁴⁴

In the construction of a tourist destination, guidebooks play an integral part in deciding what places to visit and how these should be perceived.⁴⁵ The role of the guidebook is to guide the tourist through their destination by means of planned routes, telling them which destinations are worth visiting and how these places should be experienced. In their choices of what to include and what to exclude, the authors create their own version of the destination. The quote above comes from a Swedish guidebook about travels to the Socialist Republic of Romania, published in 1969 – a mere decade after Romania had begun its large-scale investments in its tourism industry.⁴⁶ Together with other guidebooks from this time, it serves to give insight into how this relatively new travel destination was marketed, and thereby constructed, to a group of tourists that the country paid certain attention to. Drawing upon the theoretical framework of

⁴⁴ Dagmar Hellstam, *Rumänien – En reseguide* (Stockholm: Aldus/ Bonniers, 1969), 5. ”För inte så många år sedan var Rumänien ett av Europas ur turistsynpunkt mest försummade länder. Det verkade avlägset och isolerat. Nu har Rumänien öppnat sina portar på vid gavel för turisterna, och kommer med all säkerhet att räknas till 70-talets främsta turistländer.”

⁴⁵ Victoria Peel and Anders Sørensen, ed., *Exploring the Use and Impact of Travel Guidebooks* (Bristol: Channel View Publications, 2016); Scott Laderman, “Guidebooks”, in *The Routledge Companion to Travel Writing*, ed. Carl Thompson (London: Routledge, 2016), 259.

⁴⁶ The Socialist Republic of Romania will from now on be referred to as Romania.

Tourist gaze and Balkanism, this article will show how Romania was marketed in Swedish guidebooks during a formative period of its tourism industry.

The development of the tourism industry in Romania was not unique to its time.⁴⁷ The 1950s saw the establishment of charter trips to Southern Europe, offering inexperienced travellers a safe, easy and affordable way of going abroad where food, transportation, accommodation and a knowledgeable guide was included in the price.⁴⁸ The accessibility of charter trips would become the starting point of mass tourism within Europe, which in popular holiday destinations such as Mallorca meant a rapid development of their tourism infrastructure – hotels, restaurants and other tourist-oriented facilities being built at a high rate. However, these extensive constructions meant that the destinations lost their local and “authentic” atmosphere. Combined with the large crowds of tourists, it created a demand for new, less exploited destinations – a demand that many Southeastern European countries hoped to fill.⁴⁹ Countries such as Yugoslavia, Albania, Bulgaria and Romania became attractive destinations for those seeking sunny beaches with less crowds, also often to lower prices.⁵⁰ While resorts already existed in these places, catering tourists from their own and neighbouring countries, the aim of attracting Westerners came with a rapid construction of more beach resorts.⁵¹ In Romania – under the Nicolae Ceaușescu regime – Western tourists were targeted for their economic benefit, and in pursuit of improving Romania’s international profile.⁵² The state-run travel agency Carpați (ONT) had extensive responsibilities over the tourism industry, both in its infrastructure in Romania and in the contact with other countries. Historian Adelina Stefan, who has done significant research on the tourism industry of socialist Romania, has shown that apart from sun

⁴⁷ For previous research on tourism industry in Eastern Europe, see Sune Bechmann Pedersen and Christian Noack, ed., *Tourism and travel during the Cold War: negotiating tourist experiences across the Iron Curtain* (London: Routledge, 2020); Anne E. Gorsuch and Diane P. Koenker, ed., *Turizm: The Russian and East European Tourist under Capitalism and Socialism* (New York: Cornell University Press, 2006). For Yugoslavia, see Hannes Grandits and Karin Taylor, ed., *Yugoslavia’s Sunny Side: A History of Tourism in Socialism (1950s–1980s)* (Budapest: Central European University Press, 2010).

⁴⁸ Orvar Löfgren, *On Holiday: a history of vacationing* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1999), 170.

⁴⁹ Löfgren, *On Holiday*, 178.

⁵⁰ Löfgren, *On Holiday*, 180; Francesco Zavatti, “The Stalinist utopia of the Adriatic: Swedish tourists in communist Albania”, in *Tourism and Travel during the Cold War: negotiating tourist experiences across the Iron Curtain*, ed. Sune Bechman Pedersen and Christian Noack (London: Routledge, 2020).

⁵¹ Adelina Stefan, “Vacationing in the Cold War: Foreign Tourists to Socialist Romania and Franco’s Spain, 1960s–1979s” (PhD diss., University of Pittsburgh, 2016), 90.

⁵² Stefan, “Vacationing,” 2; Juliana Maxim, “Emblems of Socialism: Romania’s Black Sea Resorts, 1950s–1960s” in *Coastal Architectures and Politics of Tourism: Leisurescapes in the Global Sunbelt*, ed. Sibel Bozdoğan, Panayiota Ioanni and Petros Phōkaidēs (Taylor & Francis Complete 2022 eBooks, 2022).

holidays, ONT marketed the country on the basis of its “rich folklore and traditions.”⁵³ This is also discussed by human geographer David Turnock, who showed that contemporary tourist maps published by ONT focused on places of cultural and historical significance.⁵⁴ While many Western tourists may have initially been drawn to Romania for their sun holidays, ONT made sure to also emphasise the vast possibilities for cultural tourism.⁵⁵ As Stefan has shown, these topics were also mirrored in Western travel material on Romania, which often favoured narratives of a rich folk culture combined with Roman legacy, one source going as far as presenting the Romanians as the “Romans of the East.”⁵⁶

To reach their prospective tourists, ONT made large advertisement campaigns, publishing guidebooks, magazines, brochures and flyers in foreign languages.⁵⁷ Stefan has shown that ONT had a particular focus on attracting tourists from West Germany and Scandinavia, as they were considered promising markets.⁵⁸ Drawing attention to the Scandinavian and thereby the Swedish market was not unique to Romania. Putnik, the Yugoslav state travel agency, signed tourist agreements with five foreign tourists agencies based in different Western countries in 1947, one of which being Sweden – At first glance a seemingly peculiar choice given the country’s small population.⁵⁹ However, research has shown that Scandinavians were particularly productive travellers, as the package-tour markets of Scandinavia were the largest in Europe per capita in the mid-1960s.⁶⁰ In the case of Sweden, this can be explained by the economic growth the country saw after the end of the Second World War paired with its avoidance of devastation during the war, as it remained officially neutral throughout. Additionally Sweden remained a

⁵³ Stefan, “Vacationing,” 60.

⁵⁴ David Turnock, “Romania” in *Tourism and economic development in Eastern Europe and the Soviet Union*, ed. Derek R. Hall (London: Bellhaven Press, 1991), 207.

⁵⁵ Dragoş Petrescu, “Closely Watched Tourism: The Securitate as Warden of Transnational Encounters, 1967-9,” *Journal of Contemporary History* 50, no. 2 (2015): 337–53, 343, <http://www.jstor.org.ludwig.lub.lu.se/stable/43697378>.

⁵⁶ Stefan, “Vacationing”, 139; Adelina Stefan, “Unpacking Tourism in the Cold War: International Tourism and Commercialism in Socialist Romania, 1960s–1980s,” *Contemporary European History* 32 (2023): 381, doi:10.1017/S0960777321000540.

⁵⁷ Stefan, “Unpacking,” 378.

⁵⁸ Adelina Stefan, “The lure of capitalism: Foreign tourists and the shadow economy in Romania, 1960–1989,” in *Tourism and Travel during the Cold War: negotiating tourist experiences across the Iron Curtain*, ed. Sune Bechman Pedersen and Christian Noack (London: Routledge, 2020), 49.

⁵⁹ Igor Tchoukarine, “The Yugoslav Road to International Tourism: Opening, Decentralization, and Propaganda in the Early 1950s,” in *Yugoslav Sunny Side: A History of Tourism in Socialism (1950s-1980s)*, ed. Hannes Grandits and Karin Taylor (Budapest: Central European University Press, 2010), 110.

⁶⁰ Thomas Kaiserfeld, “From Sightseeing to Sunbathing: Changing Traditions in Swedish package tours; from Edification by Bus to Relaxation by Airplane in the 1950s and 1960s,” *Journal of Tourism History* 2 (3) (2010): 152, doi:10.1080/1755182X.2010.523147.

“neutral” country, and thus largely non-problematic country to associate with, thanks to it being part of the Non-aligned Movement during the Cold War. Furthermore, the increase in international tourism was made possible by the introduction of paid vacation, which in Sweden was legislated at two weeks in 1938, extended to three weeks in 1951, four weeks in 1963 followed by five weeks in 1978.⁶¹ This meant that going abroad became increasingly accessible not only for the upper and middle classes, but also for the working class.⁶² Perhaps due to the marketing strategies of ONT, many Swedish tourists decided to visit Romania. As historian Sune Bechmann Pedersen points out, Scandinavia accounted for 10% of tourists who visited Romania in 1974 – a disproportionate amount given the size of its population.⁶³ Given the overrepresentation of Swedish tourists to Romania, the travel material they had access to thus makes up for an interesting case study for the overall Western tourist gaze, and is also a perspective that has not been researched before.

While many Swedish tourists decided to visit Romania, it must be noted that trips to authoritarian countries did not come without controversy. For example, the Swedish travel agency Reso faced criticism for including non-democratic countries in its programmes. However, excluding these countries would mean removing some of the most popular destinations such as Francoist Spain. The supply of charter trips was therefore determined by the demands of the customers rather than the political conditions of the country.⁶⁴ For the tourist, there was thus a certain normalisation of overlooking the political conditions prevailing in their destination. The political conditions were also in general not used as a selling point for tourism.⁶⁵ Unlike what has been popularised in post-communist spaces, Bechmann Pedersen pointed out that apart from Berlin, destinations in Eastern Europe were not marketed for being places to experience the East-West divide.⁶⁶ In the case of Romania, Stefan gives an example from a French guidebook,

⁶¹ Riksdagen, Knas, SOU 2001:91, Kurt Eriksson, *Frågor om arbetstidens längd och förläggning*, 2001, <https://data.riksdagen.se/fil/3F5E65C9-C268-4675-9443-F399C728B114>, 9.

⁶² Löfgren, “On Holiday,” 170.

⁶³ Sune Bechmann Pedersen, “A Paradise behind the Curtain: Selling Eastern Escapes to Scandinavians,” in *Eden för jeden?: Touristiske Sehnsuchtsorte in Mittel- und Osteuropa von 1945 bis zur Gegenwart*, ed. Bianca Hoening and Hannah Wadle (Göttingen: V&R unipress, 2019), 228.

⁶⁴ Carina Gråbacke, *När folket tog semester: studier av Reso 1937–1977*, (Lund: Sekel Bokförlag, 2008), 211.

⁶⁵ Still, political tourism existed, often related to a quest for political gains. For an article on Folkturist, a travel agency owned by the Communist Party of Sweden, see Sune Bechmann Pedersen, “Eastbound tourism in the Cold War: the history of the Swedish communist travel agency Folkturist,” *Journal of Tourism History* 10 (2) (2018), doi: 10.1080/1755182X.2018.1469679. On the topic of ‘friendship tourism’ to Albania organised by KMFL, a splinter party of the Swedish Left Party–The Communists, see Zavatti, “Stalinist Utopia.”

⁶⁶ Bechmann Pedersen, “A Paradise,” 228.

which assured its readers that they would not even notice being “behind the Iron Curtain.”⁶⁷ The political conditions were hence largely ignored or overlooked in the marketing of Eastern Europe.

Drawing upon the existing research on the Romanian tourism industry, combined with research on the Scandinavian marketing of trips to Eastern Europe as a greater region, this article shows how Romania was marketed to Swedish tourists in the formative years of the communist rule, 1947—1989.⁶⁸ The source material consists of all eight guidebooks on Romania published in Swedish during this period, the first one in 1964 and the last in 1981.⁶⁹ Apart from one, which also covers Bulgaria, they all focus solely on Romania. They all have short and informative titles such as “Romania in your pocket”, “Romania – A guide” and “The Black Sea Riviera.” While of varying lengths and structure, all guidebooks include both practical information regarding traveling to and in the country, as well as more in depth descriptions of the culture, food, and various regions of interest. These have been analysed through a thematic approach, wherein the initial readings focused on finding commonalities and irregularities in the content. The most prevalent themes have become the basis of the structure of the article, as seen in the two main themes *Romania as a melting point of different cultural influences* and *A blend of modern and ancient*. The construction of these themes has also been influenced by the theoretical framework of the paper, being *tourist gaze* and *Balkanism*. The tourist gaze, a theory developed by John Urry and Jonas Larsen, refers to the fact that tourists see their destination with a learnt gaze, which has been constructed in the interaction between their own experiences and societal perceptions. As previously mentioned, guidebooks play an important role in the construction of these perceptions, as their presentation creates an own version of the destination, which will be the one that the tourist seeks to experience.⁷⁰ Furthermore, Urry and Larsen argue that tourists

⁶⁷ Stefan, “Vacationing,” 140.

⁶⁸ For those interested in similar studies focused on post-communist Romania, I recommend Rodica Dimitriu, “When ‘we’ are ‘the other’. Travel books on Romania as exercises in intercultural communication,” *Perspectives* 20 (3) (2012), doi: 10.1080/0907676X.2012.702400.

⁶⁹ The guidebooks, in chronological order, are Arne Häggqvist, *Svartahavsriveran : med utflykter i Rumänien och Bulgarien : badorter : sevärigheter : hotell : mat och dryck : shopping* (Stockholm: Bonnier, 1964); Kerstin Lundberg, *Rumänien – en vägledning* (Stockholm: Tidens Förlag, 1965); Ingemar Eile, *Rumänien i din ficka* (Växjö: Carl Svanberg AB, 1969); Hellstam, *Rumänien*; Agneta Uddenberg, *Rumänien* (Stockholm: Generalstabens Litografiska Anstalt, 1971); Rüdiger Von Wechmar, *Turen går till Rumänien* (Stockholm: Almqvist & Wiksell Förlag AB, 1971); Per Olof Ekström, *Hälsokällornas land – Rumänien* (Göteborg: Zindermans 1975); Heinz and Peter Göckeritz, *Rumänien* (Lund: Generalstabens Litografiska Anstalt, 1981).

⁷⁰ John Urry and Jonas Larsen, *The Tourist Gaze 3.0* (London: Sage Publications Ltd, 2012), E-book, 3.

seek out what is extraordinary in relation to their everyday lives. Therefore, their gaze is shaped by what they perceive as different.⁷¹ In this way, the gaze structures and regulates the relationship with the “other,” dictating where the dividing lines are drawn and creating a greater distance between “us” and “them.”⁷² The social imaginaries that construct the tourist gaze of Romania, include what Maria Todorova calls *Balkanism*. Definitions of the Balkan region and what countries it consists of vary according to whether one has a historical, political or geographic approach. This article follows Todorova’s definition, which includes most of former Yugoslavia, Albania, Bulgaria, Greece and Romania.⁷³ According to Todorova, the Balkans is a construction of the West, created and maintained in Western journalistic and quasi-journalistic works, not least in travel material. The Balkans is supposed to act as a bridge between ‘the West’ and ‘the Orient’, a place where aspects of these supposed opposites could meet and interact. An image is constructed of a region riddled with ambiguity and contradictions, a ‘semi-place’ that is neither fully civilised nor uncivilised, not fully modern but not fully ancient.⁷⁴ In this article, I will argue that a Balkanist discourse can be identified in the guidebooks’ depictions of Romania.

Romania as a melting point of different cultural influences

Roman heritage and the Other

Roman heritage is largely present in the depiction of Romania in the guidebooks. Reference is made to the rich history of various places – health springs that have been in use ever since the Romans, vineyards that have existed since their time, and ruins of city walls that offer glimpses of bygone times.⁷⁵ In one of the guidebooks, the Roman conquest is even used as the starting point of the country’s history.⁷⁶ When recommending sights, the Roman heritage is often emphasized. This is the case for Constanța, a coastal town where “traces of Roman times remain in many parts of the city.”⁷⁷ Two authors give a detailed presentation of a statue of Ovid, a Roman poet who lived in the city as an exile. They also point out that there are plenty of other

⁷¹ Urry and Larsen, *Tourist*, 5.

⁷² Urry and Larsen, *Tourist*, 13.

⁷³ Maria Todorova, *Imagining the Balkans* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1997), 32.

⁷⁴ Todorova, *Imagining*, 19.

⁷⁵ Eile, *Rumänien*, 29; Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 74; Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 51.

⁷⁶ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 9.

⁷⁷ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 66. ”spår från romartiden finns kvar på många håll i staden.”

statues in the city, yet both end up giving a detailed presentation only of the statue of Ovid.⁷⁸ The focus on the Roman legacy is part of a general fondness for the ancient world. The authors gladly refer to towns by their ancient Greek names – Constanța becomes Tomis and Mangalia becomes Callatis.⁷⁹ The ruins of Histria, a colony of ancient Greece, are presented as an important and fascinating site, where traces of the country's earliest settlements can be seen.⁸⁰ The greatness of this site is even more evident in the description of it as the "Pompeii of Romania."⁸¹ These recurring references give the reader the impression of a country with a history that is alive, where the ancient heritage can be sensed at every corner. In one guidebook, this is almost explicitly stated, as it refers to Constanța as a "living museum."⁸² As Roman heritage plays a vital role in Western history, this particular focus on it has a way of connecting Romania to the West. It also interacts with the way that the Romanian regime wanted to portray the history of the country. Zavatti argues that giving value to Romanian national history and vast cultural heritage was one of many offsprings of a strategy of political legitimisation aimed at building internal consensus in Romania, and a global partnership for the Romanian communist leadership.⁸³ While Roman heritage was an important part of the Romanian identity even before the rise of communism, this heritage was further emphasised by Nicolae Ceaușescu, who used it to consolidate his own power.⁸⁴

⁷⁸ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 66; Lundberg *Rumänien*, 43–44.

⁷⁹ Lundberg *Rumänien*, 43; Eile, *Rumänien*, 27.

⁸⁰ Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 90; Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 77.

⁸¹ Lundberg *Rumänien*, 41. "Rumäniens Pompeji."

⁸² Ekström, *Hälsokällornas*, 43. "ett levande museum".

⁸³ Francesco Zavatti, "Writing History in a Propaganda Institute: Political Power and Network Dynamics in Communist Romania", (PhD diss., Södertörn University, 2016), 268-270.

⁸⁴ Zavatti, "Writing History," 87.

Moskén och Ovidius staty

Image 1: Constanta Mosque with statue of Ovid in the forefront. Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 1981, 27.

Beyond the Roman heritage, the guidebooks make some reference to Turkish influences. The local mosque is highlighted as an important sightseeing spot and referred to as the “Echo of the East” – East in this context referring to the Orient.⁸⁵ A similar depiction referring to the Orient is found in another guidebook:

If you walk from the beach up to the hillside behind it, you get a flavour of the oriental atmosphere that was typical of the city in the distant past. There is a cluster of old Turkish-style houses with carved wooden balconies and bay windows.⁸⁶

Constanța is thus presented as a mixture of East and West – an example of the meeting points that can be seen within Balkanist discourse. This meeting point becomes even more telling

⁸⁵ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 44–45. ”Ekot från öst.”

⁸⁶ Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 87. ”Om man från stranden går uppför sluttningen bakom får man en fläkt av den orientaliska atmosfären som var typisk för staden i gångna tider. Där finns ett gytter av gamla hus i turkisk stil med snidande träbalkonger och burspråk.”

in an image from the 1981 guidebook, where one is shown the mosque with the silhouette of the Ovid statue in front of it.

There are major differences in the presentation of Roman and Ottoman heritage, partly reflected in its scope. While Roman influence is a recurring theme, Ottoman heritage is not mentioned as often. To the reader, the frequent presence of the Roman heritage makes it seem like a natural part of Romanian history, like something that should belong in the Romanian identity. There are mentions of “Dacian and Roman ancestry”, where the Romans become as obvious ancestors as the Dacians.⁸⁷ This is even more evident in the way this heritage is approached. For example, one author describes how the Dacian kingdom was “incorporated” into the Roman empire, resulting in the use of the Latin language. In contrast, the author goes on to say that the language was then “subjected” to Turkish and other influences.⁸⁸ Unlike the natural legacy of the Romans, Ottoman influence is a result of threat and occupation. The guidebooks tell of fortifications built to keep out the “Turks” and of the violence and conquest the country has endured from Turkish forces.⁸⁹ Portraying the Turk/Ottoman as an enemy distanced the country from that part of its heritage, while creating a clearer belonging with the West. Just as the Orient is ‘the Other’ for the West, it is also not perceived as a natural part of Romania’s historical and cultural background. Here, the authors of the guidebooks continue to follow the official Romanian narrative. As Stefan has pointed out, guidebooks written by Romanian authors emphasised Romania’s role in defeating and stopping the Ottomans in the high Middle Ages, being part of and protecting Christian Europe.⁹⁰ Similarly, these guidebooks also heavily pushed the ancient Greek and Roman legacy.⁹¹

A, for the most part, southern people

The encounter with locals can in many cases be an aspect of selling a destination. It can bring a certain sense of authenticity to the trip, and a (perceived) insight into the culture and daily life of the country. In one of the guidebooks, this encounter is described as follows:

⁸⁷ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 111–112. ”dakiska och romerska förfäder.”

⁸⁸ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 38. ”inkorporerades,” ”utsättas.”

⁸⁹ Von Wechmar, *Turen*, 32, 37; Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 60. ”turkarna.”

⁹⁰ Stefan, “Unpacking,” 377–378.

⁹¹ Stefan, “Unpacking,” 377.

One is astonished to find a lively, sociable Romanesque people, where the gentlemen kiss the ladies' hands as if it were a given, and the joie de vivre and temperament come dangerously close to that of the Italians.⁹²

When reading this description, one can sense a certain level of surprise, perhaps because the author did not expect to meet a so-called Romanesque people given their Slavic neighbours. Nevertheless, similarities with people of other Romance cultures is a recurrent theme within the guidebooks. Just as the Roman legacy has left its marks on the country, it has on the people.⁹³ At concerts, their “southern way” of showing appreciation for music is said to be noticeable.⁹⁴ Their passion and temperament is also brought up in another guidebook, making reference to their “Latin temperament.”⁹⁵ Within Balkanist discourse, one can also find stereotypes of a hot temperament, then linked to being of Slavic or Turkish descent.⁹⁶ This difference can be explained by the fact that the temperament described in the guidebooks is presented as something positive, hence Latin, whilst the Balkanist temperament is negative and connected to violence.⁹⁷

For those seeking romance, the advice given by the guidebooks is also based on the Latin roots of the people. The women are said to be beautiful and flirtatious, but the reader is advised against attempts of arranging a meeting, as they are unlikely to show up. The reason why is that they supposedly have a “morality that – despite the low importance of the Church in the country – is very similar to that we know of hyper-Catholic countries of Spain and Italy.”⁹⁸ This claim is rather peculiar, given that the Orthodox church has played a significant role in the country throughout most of its history, including the communist period.⁹⁹ However, it reflects the regime's policy at the time of the publication, which sought to weaken the role of the Church in

⁹² Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 38. ”Man finner till sin häpnad ett livligt, sällskapligt romanskt folk, där herrarna kysser damerna på hand som en självklarhet och livsglädjen och temperamentet kommer farligt nära det italienska.”

⁹³ Von Wechmar, *Turen*, 6.

⁹⁴ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 52. ”sydländska sätt.”

⁹⁵ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 7. ”latinska temperament.”

⁹⁶ Todorova, *Imagining*, 123–124.

⁹⁷ Todorova, *Imagining*, 122.

⁹⁸ Häggqvist, *Svartahavsriveran*, 8. ”en moral som – trots kyrkans ringa betydelse i landet – mycket liknar den vi känner från de hyperkatolska länderna Spanien och Italien.”

⁹⁹ Kurt Treptow and Marcel Pope, *Historical Dictionary of Romania* (London: The Scarecrow Press, 1996), 154.

Romanian society.¹⁰⁰ The author goes on to describe Romanian men, who in contrast to the women have “neither the impulsive impetuosity of the Italians nor the erotic calculation of the French.”¹⁰¹ In other words, “they are correct or shy and do not chase foreign girls.”¹⁰² These comparisons depend on the reader sharing the same gaze of Spain and Italy as highly religious countries, and stereotypes of Italian and French men as romantically savvy. The fact that the comparison is continued with stereotypes of other Latin peoples, even when the stereotypes in question do not fit the image of Romanians, suggests that they as a people belong together. It should also be emphasised that these kinds of comparisons are never made with stereotypes of Slavs, perhaps to not disturb or contradict the continuous connections made with the supposed Latin roots. At the same time, the guidebooks do mention encounters with more than just Latin temperament in the country:

And the people themselves – those who stand out most clearly after a tour become a diverse collection: the little farmer up north with a Tolstoy beard, who with a dignified bow declines a tip after a favour; peach-skinned nuns who show us around the monasteries and politely converse in French and English; the gypsy musician’s big velvet eyes as he caressingly plays out melodies next to the restaurant table...¹⁰³

The reader is presented with a picture of a country with a diverse population where one can encounter several different groups. This image fits well with the Balkanist construction of the Balkans as an area with an “inextricable medley of disparate races.”¹⁰⁴ Yet the minorities of the country rarely appear in the guidebooks. While the Hungarian and German groups are given some amount of space, the above quote is the only time the Roma minority is mentioned. An explanation to this may be the long history of discrimination and negative stereotypes towards

¹⁰⁰ Cristina Rada Irmire, “Religion and political identification in Communist Romania,” *Revista de Stiinte Politice* 2 (4) (2014): 52, <https://www.ceeol.com/search/article-detail?id=287520>.

¹⁰¹ Häggqvist, *Svartahavsriveran*, 8. “vare sig italienarens impulsiva gåpåighet eller fransmännens erotiska beräkning.”

¹⁰² Häggqvist, *Svartahavsriveran*, 8. ”De är med andra ord korrekta eller blyga och jagar inte utländska flickor.”

¹⁰³ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 7. ” Och människorna själva – de som framträder klarast efter en rundresa blir en brokig samling: den lille bonden med Tolstojkägga uppe i norr, som med en värdig bugning avböjer drickspenning efter en tjänst; persikohyade nunnor som visar runt i klostren och belevat konverserar på franska och engelska; zigenarmusikantens stora sammetsbrunnar till ögon då han smeker fram melodier vid restaurangbordet...”

¹⁰⁴ Todorova, *Imagining*, 34.

the minority in Sweden, making them a group that is not desirable to bring up when trying to market a tourist destination. The overall depiction is nevertheless of Romania as a varied and multicultural country, where the Latin roots show the clearest of all.

Transylvania as a multicultural place

In addition to Roman and Ottoman influences, Romania also shows traces of the rule of various German, Slavic and Hungarian groups throughout its history. Compared to the Roman and Ottoman, these other legacies are not as visible in the depiction of the country. The exception is the depiction of Transylvania. The region encapsulates the tumultuous history of the country, as it has for long periods been under both German and Hungarian rule. There is mention of the still existing Hungarian minority in the region, with their own distinct culture and traditions.¹⁰⁵

The importance given to the German heritage in Transylvania varies in the guidebooks. What should be noted here is that two of the guidebooks were originally written and published in German by German authors, and later translated and reworked for a Swedish audience. In these two, one notices a larger emphasis on German heritage, especially in the descriptions of the towns that were founded by them, claiming that strong cultural links still exist there.¹⁰⁶ If visiting Sibiu, one is advised to visit the German-language city theatre as well as the Brukenthal Museum, a museum with Saxon roots, claimed to be one of the most interesting museums in the country.¹⁰⁷ Similar emphasis is not found in the guidebooks originally published in Swedish. As an example, the role of the Saxon settlers in building a thriving community in Sibiu is briefly mentioned, but more attention is paid to the Roman heritage of the city.¹⁰⁸ The fact that German connections are found in German guidebooks reflects how these were originally written for a different readership, who would have been much more interested in the aspects that create a sense of community for them with Romania. Hence, one can see here a gaze constructed for a different audience than the Swedish.

¹⁰⁵ Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 63.

¹⁰⁶ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 56; Von Wechmar, *Turen*, 5.

¹⁰⁷ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 57.

¹⁰⁸ Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 59.

Due to Transylvania being a “mixture of German, Hungarian and Romanian”, one of the guidebooks calls it the most genuine part of Romania.¹⁰⁹ This description is a telling example of the presence of the Balkanist discourse. Romania is not only a meeting point of East and West, but also a place where different cultures meet and interact, despite their differences. By linking multiculturalism and authenticity, the constructed gaze is one that makes the reader expect to encounter a multicultural land, similar to how other Balkan countries are described. What is not included in this gaze, however, is the conflicts that have led to said multiculturalism. Transylvania is a region that has been disputed between Romania and Hungary since the Middle Ages.¹¹⁰ By not providing this context, the idyllic image of an interesting, multicultural place, where different groups live in harmony, can be created.

A blend of modern and ancient

Modern seaside resorts

Sol och sommar över stranden vid Mamaia, en av de populäraste badorterna vid Svarta havet

Image 2: Illustration of Mamaia, with the description “Sun and summer across the beaches at Mamaia, one of the most popular seaside resorts along the Black Sea”. Von Wechmar, *Turen går till Rumänien*, 1971, 3.

¹⁰⁹ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 116. ” en blandning av tyskt, ungerskt och rumänskt.”

¹¹⁰ Treptow and Popa, *Historical*, 202.

During the 1960s, Romanian charter tourism was on the rise. The Black Sea coast had been a popular tourist destination for the Romanian upper class throughout the 1900s.¹¹¹ In the 1950s, the state made large-scale investments for the construction of hotels and leisure environments along the coastline. This development was part of a more wide-scale democratization of vacation that began in the 1930s throughout Europe.¹¹² Hence, the Romanian seaside went from an exclusive site for the Romanian elite to a destination for the larger masses.¹¹³ A decade later, attention started to significantly be put more towards Western tourists – both for the possibility of greater revenue and international recognition, but also as an attempt to showcase how great life could be under socialism.¹¹⁴ The development of these socialist resorts are chronicled in the contemporary Swedish guidebooks, which describe how magnificent and modern hotels, restaurants, theatres and cinemas sprung up along the coast.¹¹⁵ Mamaia was the most established seaside resort at this time, and the place to which most of the charter holidays went.¹¹⁶ Enough Scandinavian tourists travelled here for the establishment of a number of hotels where only Swedes, Danes and Norwegians stayed.¹¹⁷ The rapid development of the town is described in the 1965 guidebook as follows:

The monumental, matte-white silhouette of *Hotel Parcs* introduces the hotel complex of this modern seaside resort. Before the Second World War, Mamaia had only one hotel. Now there are around thirty, almost all of the same standard. Mamaia is a town steeped in legend, but you don't need a fairytale to enjoy its charm. The soothing waves of the Black Sea lulls you to sleep in the evenings and reawakens the spirit of life in the early hours of the morning. The air is clear and fresh, the water crystal blue and cooling, leaving behind a saturated saltiness in the skin.¹¹⁸

¹¹¹ Maxim, *Emblems*, 74, 83.

¹¹² Maxim, *Emblems*, 74.

¹¹³ Maxim, *Emblems*, 74.

¹¹⁴ Stefan, "Vacationing," 2; Maxim, *Emblems*, 72.

¹¹⁵ Häggqvist, *Svartahavsrivieran*, 27.

¹¹⁶ Eile, *Rumänien*, 20.

¹¹⁷ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 30.

¹¹⁸ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 29. "Hotell Parcs monumentala, mattvita silhuett introducerar den moderna badortens hotellkomplex. Före andra världskriget hade Mamaia endast ett hotell. Nu finns där ett trettioal, alla av nästan samma standard. Mamaia är en legendomspunnen ort, med det behövs inga sagor till för att njuta av traktens charm. Svarta havets sövande bränningar vaggas till ro om kvällarna och väcker livsandarna på nytt tidiga morgontimmar. Luften är klar och frisk, vattnet klarblått och svalkande och lämnar efter sig en mättad sälta i skinnet."

Mamaia is depicted as a beautiful and peaceful place. Similarly, the 1964 guidebook showcases the town's first-class hotels and excellent beaches.¹¹⁹ The “monumental” *Hotel Parcs* was one of many newly built hotels, all in the same style and stucco as determined at state level, described as ultramodern by many of the authors.¹²⁰ However, it is not portrayed as a perfect paradise, and its flaws are linked – albeit not explicitly – to the socialist rule. These hotels are described as “standardised” and are admitted at first sight to give a “sterile impression”, referring to their ultramodern architecture and uniform furnishing.¹²¹ Even the restaurants are described as standardised, as they all have identical interiors and menus. This is also reflected in later guidebooks, which describe the hotels as “too functional.”¹²² In all of these cases, the standardisation is seen as something negative which makes the resorts lose their charm.

The last guidebook, published in 1981, also takes issue with the standards of the resorts. The high quality described in the 1960s does not seem to have been maintained. The 1981 guidebook warns its reader that they should not hope for “Western European standards” but must rather “expect things to take time to be repaired, for example, you may encounter burnt-out lightbulbs, broken wallpaper and other things you have to overlook.”¹²³ The stagnation in quality mirrors the timeline provided by Stefan – Romania investing heavily in its tourism industry until the late 1970s, when the investments saw a downturn due to both the general economic stagnation and as the regime had been unable to achieve the goals they had hoped for.¹²⁴

One issue of the seaside resorts that persists throughout the period is the lack of authenticity. This is especially remarkable, as many tourists chose countries like Romania as they hoped to have a more authentic experience than what was offered at more mainstream and popular destinations. It also clearly shows the problematic nature of the demands of “authenticity” when choosing to travel to a place solely built for tourism. By demanding what they deem as authentic, the tourist is also exoticising their destination by seeking out for it to be more different and thereby be up to their expectations. Of course, these kinds of reflections fall outside the scope of

¹¹⁹ Häggqvist, *Svartahavsrivieran*, 19.

¹²⁰ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 30; Eile, *Rumänien*, 20; Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 62.

¹²¹ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 30. ”standardiserade”, sterilt intryck.”

¹²² Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 24. ”för funktionella.”

¹²³ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 24–25. ”räkna med att det tar tid innan saker och ting lagas, man kan t ex råka ut för utbrända glödlampor, trasiga tapeter och annat man måste överse med.”

¹²⁴ Stefan, “Vacationing”, 74.

the guidebooks. In the 1965 guidebook, the atmosphere in Mamaia is described as “entirely continental and very little Romanian”.¹²⁵ The authors are careful to emphasize that one should expect nothing but intercontinental food at the hotel restaurants and recommend their readers to seek out smaller restaurants where they might actually experience genuine Romanian cuisine.¹²⁶ In the search for authenticity, however, there is one seaside resort in particular that is said to go against the trend: Mangalia. Mangalia is described as an “authentic community with a Romanian population.”¹²⁷ One of the 1969 guidebooks states that the resort is intended to be a new, larger version of Mamaia.¹²⁸ Yet in the 1981 guidebook, it is clearly stated that Mangalia is not a “hotel village” but rather a “charming small town with numerous historical remains.”¹²⁹ This statement is especially remarkable given the extent of demolition and construction that occurred in Mangalia. Architectural historian Juliana Maxim points out that the region, while described in state propaganda as a savage and uncultured land, was one of the most culturally diverse places in Europe before the construction of the resorts.¹³⁰ Mangalia in specific was the longest continuously inhabited city in Romania, with a large Turkish and Tatar population whose histories were largely removed from the urban space in favour of the construction of the resorts.¹³¹ Meanwhile, the remains of the Greek colony of Callatis were heavily emphasised, even more so as the guidebooks referred to Mangalia by the name of the ancient colony. It becomes clear that the depiction of Mangalia as a more authentic alternative had little to no actual basis in reality. As with any other resort town, any perceived “authenticity” was rather the result of the state trying to meet the needs and expectations of the tourists. In the case of Mangalia, this meant the removal of its contemporary cultural diversity in favour of exhibiting the ruins of ancient times. As the guidebooks also highlight the town as authentic, they continue the narrative of the Romanian state.

¹²⁵ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 30. ”helt kontinental och mycket lite rumänsk.”

¹²⁶ Eile, *Rumänien*, 17; Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 13; Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 104.

¹²⁷ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 76. ”ett autentiskt samhälle med rumänsk befolkning.”

¹²⁸ Eile, *Rumänien*, 27.

¹²⁹ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 36. ”hotellby”, ”charmig småstad med talrika historiska lämningar.”

¹³⁰ Maxim, *Emblems*, 82.

¹³¹ Maxim, *Emblems*, 82.

Health spas – Modern science with historic legacy

Just as seaside resorts were popular destinations, the Romanian thermal spas were of great interest to the Western tourist – interesting enough for there to be a guidebook with them as its sole focus.¹³² Their popularity reflects the investments made by the Romanian state in its health resorts after the Second World War, precisely with the aim of attracting more tourists.¹³³ In the presentation of the health resorts, there is a strong emphasis on the scientific basis of the treatments and the involvement of specialists, ensuring that all of them are run by “specially trained doctors.”¹³⁴ “Health-giving” springs are promised to benefit those struggling with everything from rheumatism and heart disease to digestive problems and liver disorders.¹³⁵ The clinics are supposedly modern with equipment that is up to date.¹³⁶ The authors also emphasize the cooperation between Swedish and Romanian doctors, which gives a further boost in confidence to the treatments.¹³⁷

The history of the spas is also of great importance to the authors. The treatments performed are not “some new miracle method” but rather techniques that supposedly go back over 2000 years.¹³⁸ Baile Herculane is marketed as one of the country’s most traditional spas. There, one can bathe in the same thermal springs that were used by the Romans, while overlooking a statue of Hercules.¹³⁹ The marketing creates an image of spas that are both ancient and modern, an interplay between the old and the new, reinforcing this common theme.

Bucharest – A capital in transition

A trip to the country’s capital is a staple in the guidebooks, all of which have a dedicated section on Bucharest. In their depictions, the city is a mixture of opposites – old meets new, greenery meets industry, and Parisian elements meet Stalinist architecture.

¹³² Ekström, *Hälsokällornas*.

¹³³ George Erdeli, Ana Irina Dincă, Aurel Gheorghilaş, Camelia Surugiu, “Romanian Spa Tourism: A Communist Paradigm in a Post Communist Era,” *Journal of Studies and Research in Human Geography* 5 (2) (2011): 43, doi: 10.5719/hgeo.2011.52.41.

¹³⁴ Von Wechmar, *Turen*, 19. ”specialutbildade läkare.”

¹³⁵ Von Wechmar, *Turen*, 19. ”Hälsobringande.”

¹³⁶ Ekström, *Hälsokällornas*, 25.

¹³⁷ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 55.

¹³⁸ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 55.

¹³⁹ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 70.

The authors are not shy of calling the city the “Paris of the Balkans” or “Little Paris.”¹⁴⁰ The city – with its wide avenues and boulevards, and a triumphal arc – has a “continental flavour” supposedly similar to Paris.¹⁴¹ The use of this epithet is not unique to the guidebooks, as the city has been compared to Paris since the nineteenth century. Bucharest has been the capital of Romania since its independence in 1878. Notwithstanding the multiple rulers with different ideologies that came to power, the development of the city has since then been constant.¹⁴² These developments were made with great inspiration from the latest urban and architectural trends in France and Italy, to continue showcasing the alleged Latin roots and historical ties with Western Europe.¹⁴³ Similarly, Bucharest acted as an important cultural centre, where French culture was particularly sought after.¹⁴⁴ The guidebooks provide the same image of a highly cultural city, with an unusual number of museums and a vibrant opera and theatre scene.¹⁴⁵ Hence, the authors support and thereby continue the image constructed by the Romanian state.

Another sign of the Parisian city planning is the labelling of Bucharest as a green metropolis.¹⁴⁶ The first impression is of “greenery, light, airiness”, in a city where cleanliness is said to have been a priority, with a successful anti-litter law and streets washed daily.¹⁴⁷ The guidebooks emphasise the many parks and lakes, which give the city a certain sense of calm.¹⁴⁸ When new neighbourhoods are built, they are designed with the preservation of green spaces in mind.¹⁴⁹ However, this seemingly verdant city is also said to be an industrial centre, accounting for 20% of the state’s industrial output.¹⁵⁰ It is mentioned that some 50 new industries had been built since 1948.¹⁵¹ This remark becomes one of the clearest references to the prevailing

¹⁴⁰ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 59.

¹⁴¹ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 59; Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 29; Häggqvist, *Svartahavsriveran*, 38; Von Wechmar, *Turen*, 25. ”kontinental prägel.”

¹⁴² Maria Raluca Popa, “Bucharest,” in *Capital Cities in the Aftermath of Empires*, ed. Emily Gunzburger Makaš and Tanja Damljanović Conley (Taylor & Francis e-Library, 2009), E-book, 62.

¹⁴³ Popa, “Bucharest,” 62.

¹⁴⁴ Roxana Verona, “Bucharest at the crossroad” *Publications of the Modern Language Association of America* 122 (1) 76, <http://ludwig.lub.lu.se/login?url=https://www.jstor.org/stable/25501688>.

¹⁴⁵ Von Wechmar, *Turen*, 25; Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 69.

¹⁴⁶ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 16.

¹⁴⁷ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 59; Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 81. ”grönska, ljus, luftighet.”

¹⁴⁸ Häggqvist, *Svartahavsriveran*, 38.

¹⁴⁹ Eile, *Rumänien*, 33.

¹⁵⁰ Häggqvist, *Svartahavsriveran*, 38; Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 59; Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 81.

¹⁵¹ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 81.

industrialization that Romania underwent during the period, a significant part in their process of modernisation.¹⁵² It also stands as a clear contradiction to the imagery of the city as green.

In 1965, Bucharest was described as a “changing city with a pleasant mixture of old and new”, where “old unsanitary residential areas are being demolished to make way for new complexes with central heating and all the modern conveniences” and where neighbourhoods are growing at an “explosive speed.”¹⁵³ In the guidebooks, Bucharest is generally portrayed as a relatively young city, where culturally significant buildings are no older than 400 years.¹⁵⁴ The city is said to be devoid of Romanesque and Gothic styles, as much of it had been destroyed by war and earthquakes.¹⁵⁵ The buildings mentioned in the various books show influences from several places and periods – neo-Gothicism, French Renaissance and Greek Church art.¹⁵⁶ Socialist rule is also presented, with descriptions of buildings in Stalinist style.¹⁵⁷ Overall, the impression is of a city in transition, with influences from many directions, which is in many ways similar to how the country is generally portrayed. In the construction of the new, the memory of the old prevails. The reader is left with a conflicting picture of the Romanian capital, a supposedly green, cultural and beautiful Balkan-version of Paris with its older architecture, while simultaneously being a city full of industry and construction. In a sense, the authors capture the process of transition that not only the capital was undergoing, but also the entire country.

A countryside stuck in the past

Beyond the polished surface of the seaside resorts and the complexity of its capital, one finds the Romanian countryside. According to the authors, the countryside is where it is possible to experience the most authentic version of Romania. The authenticity experienced in Transylvania, as discussed earlier, is largely based on the region’s multiculturalism, but also concerning how it has preserved its traditions and a more old-fashioned way of life. In smaller communities across

¹⁵² Eric J. Hobsbawm, *Ytterligheternas tidsålder: det korta 1900-talet: 1914–1991* (Stockholm: Rabén Prisma, 1997), 298, 331–332.

¹⁵³ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 60. ”föränderlig stad med behaglig blandning av gammalt och nytt”, ” Gamla osanitära bostadsområden rivs för att lämna plats åt nya komplex med centralvärme och alla moderniteter”, ” explosiv fart.”

¹⁵⁴ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 16.

¹⁵⁵ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 16.

¹⁵⁶ Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 35; Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 19.

¹⁵⁷ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 20.

the country, it is possible to see a simpler way of life, steeped in tradition. It is an experience recommended to all kinds of travellers, even those whose plans might just be to visit the beach, as a trip to the countryside is the best way to get closer to the country.¹⁵⁸

In the countryside, the tourist will encounter a very different world to that they are used to back in Sweden, one that seems to have been isolated from the development of the rest of the world.¹⁵⁹ The traffic on the roads consist of “all kinds of carts, sheep, geese, cows, and little girls, who in the villages use the country road as a place for community.”¹⁶⁰ The architecture is different depending on the region, and is said to be a “manifestation of the collective, deeply rooted in everyday material” – a spiritual, social, and cultural environment.¹⁶¹ In the description of Maramureş, one author goes as far as likening someone’s home to an ethnographic museum:

The old-fashioned villages are characterised by small wooden houses, built of horizontal logs, with high thatched or shingled roofs and finely sculpted verandas with lots of flowers. Cross the threshold of the house and you enter a small ethnographic museum. The people have a deep love for fabrics. They cover floors, tables, beds and walls.¹⁶²

¹⁵⁸ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 20.

¹⁵⁹ Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 63.

¹⁶⁰ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 20. ”alla tänkbara kärror, får, gäss, kossor och små gummor, som i byarna använder landsvägen som ett enda gemensamt sällskapsrum.”

¹⁶¹ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 111–112. ”manifestation av kollektivet, djup rotfast vid vardagsmaterial, andlig, social och kulturell miljö.”

¹⁶² Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 67–68. ”Byarnas ålderdomliga bebyggelse karaktiseras av små trähus, byggda av liggande stockar, med höga halm- eller spåntak och fint skulpterade verandor med mängder av blommor. Går man över husets tröskel kommer man in ett litet etnografiskt museum. Människorna har en djup kärlek till vävnader. De täcker golv, bord, sängar och väggar.”

Image 3 (on the left): Cover of Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 1971, an illustration of men in traditional clothing playing instruments and dancing.

Image 4 (on the right): Cover of Von Wechmar, *Turen går till Rumänien*, 1971, an illustration of a woman in traditional clothing and a headscarf.

This portrayal reflects the tourist gaze we have, and create, around the countryside as an old-fashioned place steeped in folk culture. The houses, which are likened to museums, become objects for the tourist to enjoy. Similarly, one can look towards the portrayal of the people, who are repeatedly described as wearing folk costumes on a daily basis.¹⁶³ Traditional clothing often appears in the illustrations and images in the guidebooks, and can be seen on the covers of many of them. The use of something as traditional as folk costumes, which are even said to be worn while working in the fields, becomes an affirmation of their gaze, and therefore an important part of their narrative.¹⁶⁴

¹⁶³ Von Wechmar, *Turen*, 10; Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 7; Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 67.

¹⁶⁴ Von Wechmar, *Turen*, 10.

Similarly, the culture and way of life of the people are presented in a way that confirms this view. Romania is described as the country with the richest folklore in Europe, where folk music and dance permeate everyday life.¹⁶⁵ A picture is painted of an utmost vibrant countryside, where people feel a strong connection to music, culture and tradition. According to one of the authors, this strong bond stems from the many centuries of external threats and invasions that the country has endured, periods when culture was the only thing that could hold the Romanian people together.¹⁶⁶ Traditions have been preserved, not least in terms of wedding celebrations. Wedding ceremonies have supposedly not lost any of their originality, still faithful to old traditions.¹⁶⁷ In one of the guidebooks, one can read about the wedding garments, emphasising the great details of these home-made costumes:

The groom, the bride and the entire bridal party are dressed in their hand-woven and home-stitched traditional costumes. Trousers, skirts, blouses, aprons, hats, shoes and boots – everything is embroidered and embellished, sometimes in muted colours, but usually in bright colours, giving free reign to the anonymous creative spirit of the people.¹⁶⁸

The author goes on to describe an ancient tradition that is said to still be followed, where the man hires, “according to custom, a group of men to guard her [the bride] against ‘evildoers’ who want to ‘steal’ her away.”¹⁶⁹ This traditional peasant wedding can be contrasted with a wedding experienced by another author at a restaurant in Bucharest, who disappointedly tells their reader that the wedding couple was very Westernised in their attire.¹⁷⁰ She goes on to point out that one has to go to the countryside to experience the weddings that follow old traditions – those that are

¹⁶⁵ Von Wechmar, *Turen*, 10; Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 7; Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 112.

¹⁶⁶ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 7.

¹⁶⁷ Von Wechmar, *Turen*, 10.

¹⁶⁸ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 99. ”Såväl brudgummen som bruden och hela brudföljet är klädda i sina handvävda och hemsömmade folkdräkter. Byxor, kjortlar, blusar, förkläden, hattar, skor och stövlar – allt är broderat och utsmyckat, ibland i nerdämpade färger, men oftast i granna kulörer, där befolkningens anonyma skaparlynnne fått fritt utlopp.”

¹⁶⁹ Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 99–100. ”enligt hävd en skara män att vakta henne mot ’illasinnade’, som vill ’röva bort’ henne”.

¹⁷⁰ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 32.

authentically Romanian.¹⁷¹ In the eyes of the authors, Romanian weddings should clearly not have any signs of Western contact. As the countryside, they should preserve their own culture and traditions, keeping a sense of authenticity for the tourists to experience.

A modernity in the making

Romania's attachment to its traditions stood out as an important selling point for the Swedish tourist. As 'the hustle and bustle' had not yet reached this seemingly untouched land, it offered an escape from modernity and everything that it brought. Romania presented an opportunity to experience a simpler, more traditional way of life, where people still dressed in traditional clothing in their everyday lives. While romanticising this image, the authors also raise concerns about how long this kind of life will continue, since Romania was also a country in transition. Hence, they express a certain sense of urgency for those who want to experience this authenticity: "You have to hurry to experience the old before the hustle and bustle of time, modernisation and industrialisation have erased the still existing patina, charged with historical memories."¹⁷²

Modernisation and industrialisation are portrayed as a threat to the ancient culture and traditions that the country has to offer. Remarkably, it is the 1981 guidebook, published after two decades of rapid modernisation and industrialisation, that raises this concern.¹⁷³ Thus, it becomes questionable how truthful this representation was, and if it was not rather about what the author wanted Romania to be. Romania, as a place where modernity has not yet reached, fits well into the Balkanist discourse of a semi-civilised region who has not come as far as the Western sphere. The process of modernisation becomes something negative, as it goes against what the country should be – without its antiquity it loses its authenticity. Rather than highlighting the positive effects of modernisation, they romanticise the aspects of a 'simpler' life, without the stresses of modernity experienced at home. Romania thus takes on a symbolic role of the longing for simpler times.

¹⁷¹ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 32.

¹⁷² Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 4. "Man måste skynda för att få uppleva det gamla innan tidens jäkt, moderniseringen, industrialiseringen suddat ut den patina, som ännu finns, laddad av historiska minnen."

¹⁷³ Hobsbawn, *Ytterligheternas*, 298, 331–332.

Unlike at home

In selling a destination, it is also important that the guidebook can recognise any shortcomings and things to be prepared for that might be of importance in the planning of the trip. In the case of Romania, this mainly concerns consumer goods and their availability. On the topic of what one should bring with them from home, some suggest items such as nylon stockings and cosmetics, as these are said to be both expensive and of low quality in Romania.¹⁷⁴ Others highlight that consumer products like those make excellent gifts for the helpful service staff, as they are sought-after items that are otherwise difficult to obtain for Romanians.¹⁷⁵ Through these recommendations, the authors reflect the reality of living in contemporary, communist Romania, which completely de-prioritised the production and import of consumer goods.¹⁷⁶ Likewise, the reader is discouraged from buying clothes in the country, as its fashion is described as very different from what one would expect at home:

However, if you want to experience the latest fashion, be up to date by reading Swedish newspapers and have everything that you are used to at home, Romania may not be on your mind. Romania is an Eastern state where much differs from what is available at home.¹⁷⁷

In the quote above, the differences encountered are explicitly explained by the country being an Eastern state – a term that is rarely encountered otherwise. In general, Romania being a communist and *Eastern* state seems like something that the authors seek to avoid. Apart from concise introductory information on the governing of the country, it is a topic that is only brought up in relation to fashion and consumer goods.¹⁷⁸ It is only relevant when it affects the tourist. Simultaneously, the lack of consumer goods and differences in fashion become further evidence of the difference in modernity between Romania and Sweden. In contrast to the negative

¹⁷⁴ Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 10.

¹⁷⁵ Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 37; Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 119.

¹⁷⁶ Stefan, "The lure", 51–52.

¹⁷⁷ Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 4. "Däremot har man kanske inte Rumänien i tankarna om man vill uppleva senaste modet, följa med vad som händer i svenska tidningar och ha allt som man är van vid hemifrån. Rumänien är en öststat där mycket avviker från det man har på hemmaplan."

¹⁷⁸ Häggqvist, *Svartahavsriveran*, 7; Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 24; Von Wechmar, *Turen*, 6.

attitudes towards the modernisation that ‘threatens’ the countryside, it is also an example of how the country could actually benefit from some level of modernisation. Once again, one can see how the depiction of Romania – in what is perceived as positive and negative – solely relies on the needs and expectations of the tourist.

Romania as a Balkanist blend of contradictions

In this article, the main aspects of the tourist gaze, created and maintained by the contemporary Swedish guidebooks, have been discussed. These aspects reflect the Balkanist discourse that was assumed to be the basis of the gaze. In the interplay between East and West, and the ancient and modern, the authors of guidebooks construct an image of a semi-place that, with its Western influences, is reminiscent of one’s own, yet has enough differences to not be considered fully part of it. As the Balkanist discourse proposes, the depiction of Romania is of a place where the Western and Eastern influences meet – Oriental influences interact with reminders of ancient Western history to make cities like Constanța be sold as interesting destinations. Similarly, German and Hungarian minorities are portrayed in a way to depict a country of great multiculturalism. Yet, it is precisely Roman heritage that becomes the most evident in the guidebooks – both in their portrayal of people and places. By focusing on the heritage shared with the West – just like other Western guidebooks did – a sense of commonality is created. This is furthered by the depiction of the Orient as an enemy – for Romanians, the Ottoman legacy is not voluntary but rather the result of violence and occupation. As Francesco Zavatti has shown in his research, contemporary Romanian historiography also pushed the Roman legacy. According to Zavatti, the regime was able to consolidate its power by creating an image of a nation that was “ancient, unchanged, independent, and united”, wherein Nicolae Ceaușescu was responsible for protecting this.¹⁷⁹ Adelina Stefan has shown that this was also pushed in the state-published guidebooks written in foreign languages, where much emphasis was put on Romanian folk culture as well as the Roman heritage.¹⁸⁰ With this in mind, one can question the role the Romanian state played in the construction of the gaze pushed by the Swedish guidebooks. Given the total monopoly that ONT had over the Romanian tourism industry, it is undeniable that the

¹⁷⁹ Zavatti, “Writing history,” 2016, p.268.

¹⁸⁰ Stefan, “Unpacking,” 377.

authors would have encountered it – also evident by them repeatedly making reference to them.¹⁸¹ Similarities can also be seen in terms of how the guidebooks present culture and tradition. Just like Stefan and Turnock argue that folk culture was an important selling point for ONT, it played an essential role in the depiction of ‘authentic’ Romania in the guidebooks.¹⁸² There is a clear overlap between how Romania wanted to present itself and how it was subsequently presented in the guidebooks. To gain more insight into the connections between ONT and the Swedish travel material, future research could consult archival material both from Sweden and Romania, investigating material from diplomatic missions and World fairs.

The Balkanist discourse is most evident in the way that the authors treat the interplay between the old traditions and the modern. In their gaze, it is precisely Romania’s continued strong connection to traditions and their seemingly ‘simpler’ lives that become important aspects of the ‘genuine’ Romania, which is also what the guidebooks argue must be experienced. By describing country roads mainly used by carriages and animals, and villagers still dressed in traditional clothing who live in houses described as museums, the authors create an image of a countryside where time has stood still. This image is heavily romanticised, symbolising what has been lost in the West. In this way, the ‘own’ is reflected in the description of Romania. The old-fashionedness of Romania must be preserved, shown by their rejection of modernisation as a threat to what the country *should* be. When modernity is portrayed in a positive way, it is done solely from the perspective of the tourist – spa treatments being based on state-of-the-art science clearly strengthens the confidence in them, as do modern hotel facilities at seaside resorts. This creates an ownership of the country, dictating when modernity is positive and negative based on what is favourable to the tourist rather than the citizens.

In the search for what the authors emphasise in their representations of the country, it also becomes clear what they choose to exclude. In line with what Sune Bechmann Pedersen writes about Eastern Europe as a whole, and as Adelina Stefan has shown to be true in the example of a French guidebook covering Romania, the communist rule is not marketed as a reason to visit the country.¹⁸³ Rather, it is a topic that for the most part is avoided – briefly mentioned in the introductions and to then barely be noticeable. As Carina Gråbacke argues, many tourists did not

¹⁸¹ For mentions of ONT in the guidebooks, see Lundberg, *Rumänien*, 37, 49, 92; Uddenberg, *Rumänien*, 19, 23; Göckeritz, *Rumänien*, 22; Eile, *Rumänien*, 16; Hellstam, *Rumänien*, 8.

¹⁸² Turnock, “Romania”, 207; Stefan, “Vacationing”, 60.

¹⁸³ Bechmann Pedersen, “Paradise”, 244–245; Stefan, “Vacationing”, 140.

care too much about the political situation in their chosen destination, as the most popular charter trips by the travel agency Reso were those going to places such as Francoist Spain.¹⁸⁴ Furthermore, as Bechmann Pedersen points out, this may be because guidebooks preferred to avoid controversial topics that could make the publication of the book more difficult, or merely because it could negatively affect the image of the country.¹⁸⁵ Despite its distancing from the Soviet Union, Romania was after all a country belonging to the Eastern bloc during a relatively uncertain period of European history. By sparingly using terms related to this contemporary division of Europe, the authors may have given the impression that it was of little importance for the tourist. The reader is most likely to realise that it is a communist country they are reading about when on the topic of what they should bring from home, as the authors emphasise the lack of certain consumer goods. The only depiction of the results of the communist rule were those that could affect the tourist.

Overall, this study has given insight in the construction and maintenance of the tourist gaze of Romania, evidently permeated by Balkanist discourse. As often is the case with travel literature, the authors take ownership of the country in question and depict it with the intended audience in mind. It is therefore not exceptional that these different guidebooks all offer quite a homogenous depiction and description of Romania, being as they are all having the same nordic-germanic audience in mind. The findings on how Romania is depicted in these guidebooks also goes in line with previous research on other Western European gazes. While guidebooks play a vital role in the construction of a gaze of a country, they are not lone actors in this. For a more encompassing image of the construction of the tourist gaze of Romania, future research should both examine a wider range of travel material – such as travelogues, travel posters, advertisements and charter programmes – as well World fairs and other official state representations abroad.

¹⁸⁴ Gråbacke, “När folket,” 211.

¹⁸⁵ Sune Bechmann Pedersen and Christian Noack, “Crossing the Iron Curtain: an introduction,” in *Tourism and Travel during the Cold War: negotiating tourist experiences across the Iron Curtain*, ed. Sune Bechman Pedersen and Christian Noack (London: Routledge, 2020), 3.

Source material

Eile, Ingemar. *Rumänien i din ficka*. Växjö: Carl Svanberg AB, 1969.

Ekström, Per Olof. *Hälsokällornas land – Rumänien*. Göteborg: Zindermans 1975.

Göckeritz, Heinz och Peter Göckeritz. *Rumänien*. Lund: Generalstabens Litografiska Anstalt, 1981.

Hellstam, Dagmar. *Rumänien – En reseguide*. Stockholm: Aldus/ Bonniers, 1969.

Häggqvist, Arne. *Svartahavsrivieran : med utflykter i Rumänien och Bulgarien : badorter : sevärdheter : hotell : mat och dryck : shopping*. Stockholm: Bonnier, 1964.

Lundberg, Kerstin. *Rumänien – en vägledning*. Stockholm: Tidens Förlag, 1965.

Uddenberg, Agneta. *Rumänien*. Stockholm: Generalstabens Litografiska Anstalt, 1971.

Von Wechmar, Rüdiger. *Turen går till Rumänien*. Stockholm: Almqvist & Wiksell Förlag AB, 1971.

Bibliography

Bechmann Pedersen, Sune. “A Paradise behind the Curtain: Selling Eastern Escapes to Scandinavians.” In *Eden für jeden?: Touristische Sehnsuchtsorte in Mittel- und Osteuropa von 1945 bis zur Gegenwart*, edited by Bianca Hoening and Hannah Wadle, 227–249. Göttingen: V&R unipress, 2019.

Bechmann Pedersen, Sune. “Eastbound Tourism in the Cold War: the History of the Swedish Communist Travel Agency Folk turist.” *Journal of Tourism History* 10, no.2 (2018): 130–145. doi: 10.1080/1755182X.2018.1469679.

Bechmann Pedersen, Sune and Noack, Christian, eds. *Tourism and travel during the Cold War: negotiating tourist experiences across the Iron Curtain*. London: Routledge, 2020.

- Dimitriu, Rodica. "When 'we' are 'the other'. Travel books on Romania as exercises in intercultural communication." *Perspectives* 20, no.3 (2012): 313–327. doi: 10.1080/0907676X.2012.702400.
- Erdeli, George, Ana Irina Dincă, Aurel Gheorghilaș, and Camelia Surugiu. "Romanian Spa Tourism: A Communist Paradigm in a Post Communist Era." *Journal of Studies and Research in Human Geography* 5, no.2 (2011): 41–56. doi: 10.5719/hgeo.2011.52.41.
- Gorsuch, Anne E. and Koenker, Diane P., eds. *Turizm: The Russian and East European Tourist under Capitalism and Socialism*. New York: Cornell University Press, 2006.
- Grandits, Hannes and Taylor, Karin, eds. *Yugoslavia's Sunny Side: A History of Tourism in Socialism (1950s–1980s)*. Budapest: Central European University Press, 2010.
- Gråbacke, Carina. *När folket tog semester: studier av Reso 1937-1977*. Lund: Sekel Bokförlag, 2008.
- Irmire, Rada Christina. "Religion and political identification in Communist Romania." *Revista de Stiinte Politice* 2, no.4 (2014), 47–63. <https://www.cceol.com/search/article-detail?id=287520>.
- Kaiserfeld, Thomas. "From Sightseeing to Sunbathing: Changing Traditions in Swedish package tours; from Edification by Bus to Relaxation by Airplane in the 1950s and 1960s." *Journal of Tourism History* 2, no.3 (2010): 149–63. doi:10.1080/1755182X.2010.523147.
- Laderman, Scott. "Guidebooks." In *The Routledge Companion to Travel Writing*, edited by Carl Thompson, 258–269. London: Routledge, 2015.
- Löfgren, Orvar. *On Holiday: a history of vacationing*. Berkeley: University of California Press, 1999.
- Maxim, Juliana. "Emblems of Socialism: Romania's Black Sea Resorts, 1950s-1960s." In *Coastal Architectures and Politics of Tourism: Leisurescapes in the Global Sunbelt*, edited by Sibel Bozdoğan, Panayiota Ioanni and Petros Phōkaidēs, 71–86, New York: Taylor & Francis Complete 2022 eBooks, 2022.

Peel, Victoria and Sørensen, Anders, eds. *Exploring the Use and Impact of Travel Guidebooks*. Bristol: Channel View Publications, 2016.

Petrescu, Dragoș. “Closely Watched Tourism: The Securitate as Warden of Transnational Encounters, 1967-9.” *Journal of Contemporary History* 50, no. 2 (2015): 337–53, <http://www.jstor.org.ludwig.lub.lu.se/stable/43697378>.

Popa, Maria Raluca. “Bucharest.” In *Capital Cities in the Aftermath of Empires*, edited by Emily Gunzburger Makaš and Tanja Damljanović Conley, 61–74. Taylor & Francis e-Library, 2009. E-book.

Riksdagen, Knas, SOU 2001:91, Kurt Eriksson, Frågor om arbetstidens längd och förläggning, 2001, <https://data.riksdagen.se/fil/3F5E65C9-C268-4675-9443-F399C728B114>.

Stefan, Adelina. “The lure of capitalism: Foreign tourists and the shadow economy in Romania, 1960-1989.” In *Tourism and Travel during the Cold War: negotiating tourist experiences across the Iron Curtain*, edited by Sune Bechman Pedersen and Christian Noack, 47–60. London: Routledge, 2020.

Stefan, Adelina. “Unpacking Tourism in the Cold War: International Tourism and Commercialism in Socialist Romania, 1960s–1980s.” In *Contemporary European History* 32 (2023): 365–384. doi:10.1017/S0960777321000540.

Stefan, Adelina. *Vacationing in the Cold War: Foreign Tourists to Socialist Romania and Franco’s Spain, 1960s-1979s*. PhD diss., University of Pittsburgh 2016.

Tchoukarine, Igor. “The Yugoslav Road to International Tourism: Opening, Decentralization, and Propaganda in the Early 1950s.” In *Yugoslav Sunny Side: A History of Tourism in Socialism (1950s-1980s)*, edited by Hannes Grandits and Karin Taylor, 107–140. Budapest: Central European University Press, 2010.

Todorova, Maria. *Imagining the Balkans*. New York: Oxford University Press, 1997.

Treptow, Kurt and Marcel Pope. *Historical Dictionary of Romania*. London: The Scarecrow Press, 1996.

Turnock, David. "Romania." In *Tourism and economic development in Eastern Europe and the Soviet Union*, edited by Derek R. Hall, 203–219. London: Bellhaven Press, 1991.

Urry, John and Jonas Larsen. *The Tourist Gaze 3.0*. London: Sage Publications Ltd, 2012, E-book.

Verona, Roxana. "Bucharest at the Crossroads." *Publications of the Modern Language Association of America* 122, no.1 (2007), 275–280.
<http://ludwig.lub.lu.se/login?url=https://www.jstor.org/stable/25501688>.

Zavatti, Francesco. "The Stalinist utopia of the Adriatic: Swedish tourists in communist Albania." In *Tourism and Travel during the Cold War: negotiating tourist experiences across the Iron Curtain*, edited by Sune Bechman Pedersen and Christian Noack, 139–156. London: Routledge, 2020.

Zavatti, Francesco. *Writing History in a Propaganda Institute: Political Power and Network Dynamics in Communist Romania*. PhD diss., Södertörn University, 2016.